

NONLINEAR BEHAVIOR OF POLYMERS AND STRUCTURES PRODUCED USING ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) builds polymer structures through layer-by-layer deposition, enabling the production of fiber-reinforced composites with enhanced strength. However, due to inherent polymer behaviors such as creep, shrinkage, and aging, 3D-printed components are prone to long-term deformation. These effects are amplified by the anisotropic, composite-like nature of printed structures, where filaments are only partially bonded. This research investigates the long-term viscoelastic and viscoplastic behavior of FFF-printed polymers to improve structural reliability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive manufacturing of polymers and their structures has been a fast-growing research space, with more than 100,000 papers published last year, and the industry due to the significant advantages over other manufacturing methods, e.g., design freedom, significant waste and energy reduction. This method offers high flexibility with the prototyping and optimization of different shapes, thus extending the applicability of polymers. With Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF), the polymer structure is built layer-by-layer through the deposition of feedstock materials. The FFF can be used to produce fiber composite structures with increased strength, further increasing the applications of this manufacturing method.

Despite these advantages, polymers produced with the FFF method have shown significant time-dependent behavior [1]. Part of the nonlinearity can be attributed to the material behavior itself, but a large part is due to the complex internal structure. Each printed filament is only partially bonded to the neighboring filaments, thus forming long aligned fibers, a composite-like structure (Figure 1) and creating an anisotropic material. Due to the novelty of this manufacturing method, these effects have not been studied, especially with regard to different environmental and material state effects. Appropriate modeling methods and models for these 3D printed structures have not been developed.

The most widely used nonlinear viscoelastic (VE) material models have been developed by Scapery [2], [3], [4]. In [5], it was modified to include the Zapas model for viscoplasticity [6] and damage and has been successfully used to simulate different materials 1D time-dependent behavior [7], [8].

$$\varepsilon = d(\sigma_{max}) \cdot \left(\varepsilon_0 + g_1 \int_0^t \Delta S(\psi - \psi') \frac{d(g_2 \sigma)}{d\tau} d\tau + \varepsilon_{VP}(\sigma, t) \right) \quad (1)$$

Where	$d(\sigma_{max})$	Effect of damage
	ε_0	Elastic strain in undamaged composite
	g_1, g_2	Stress dependent material properties
	$\Delta S(\psi)$	Time dependent part of the viscoelastic response, transient component of the linear viscoelastic creep compliance
	ψ	Reduced time
	ε_{VP}	Viscoplastic strain

It has shown high adaptability, which is crucial for modeling various environmental conditions. The complexity of different structures with 3D stress states demands models and tools able to predict 3D stress states [9]. Various models have been integrated into finite element method (FEM) to simulate stress and strain behavior under monotonic and uniaxial loading conditions [10], [11]. However, a more realistic 3D nonlinear material modeling tool, able to predict nonlinear VE response, is yet to be developed. In [9], this model was adapted for the 3D case.

In the modeling of material behavior, the balance between accuracy and complexity is a key consideration. While highly detailed models may offer precise predictions, they often require extensive parameter calibration and computational resources. The simplicity of models characterized by a minimal number of parameters is advantageous, as it facilitates implementation and reduces computational overhead by eliminating the need for complex optimization procedures [12]. Such models are also easier to interpret, validate, and apply in practical scenarios, especially when data availability is limited or computational efficiency is a priority.

Within this study, we tested the material at different stages (before printing and after printing) and scales (single filament and printed structures) of manufacturing. Statistical characterization showed nonlinear behavior for all sample groups. The elastic properties showed slightly higher values for printed filament and specimens than for filament as received. Uploading time to reach the load in the creep test result in higher initial strain values and more pronounced recovery behavior, indicating time-dependent viscoelastic effects. Creep compliances obtained from creep tests showed nonlinear viscoelastic behavior already at low stress levels, further proving the need for the use of nonlinear viscoelastic material models.

Figure 1: Cross section of the printed specimen (left) and various Specimen types (right) starting from the top Thick Filament (Y), Single extruded filament (F) and rectangular – printed (smaller) and cut-out of larger printed plate (larger ones) for both directions 0° (L) and 90° (T)

Figure 2: Printing schematic of layers

2 MATERIALS

The plastic industry is moving towards more sustainable alternatives and replacing non-renewable plastics and oil with competitive bio-based materials [13]. Within our study, we used Ultimaker Tough Black Polylactic acid (PLA), a technical PLA filament, which has been used. The PLA has a glass transition temperature of 62 °C, a melt temperature of 151 °C.

Material at three different phases of manufacturing has been used in the study (Figure 1):

- a) Thick Filament as received from the manufacturer (Y);
- b) Single filament printed using 3D printer (F);
- c) Rectangular 3D printed specimens ($L_{\text{printed}}/T_{\text{printed}}$);
- d) Cut-out of large 3D printed rectangular plate ($L_{\text{cut-out}}/T_{\text{cut-out}}$).

The specimens were manufactured using the Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) technique, which is an additive manufacturing technique that uses a continuous filament of thermoplastic material. The filament is fed from a spool through a heated printer extruded head, which melts the material and deposits it layer by layer to build a 3D object. The print head moves in two dimensions to create each horizontal layer, and then the platform or head moves vertically to add subsequent layers (Figure 2).

Specimens were printed and kept in an enclosed environment, away from sunlight. All specimens were printed using the Ultimaker-2C-3AC2 model (Ultimaker B.V., The Netherlands). Specimens were printed using a 0.4 mm linewidth. The infill pattern was set to “Lines” with a specimen infill density of 100 %, layer thickness of 0.1 mm, printing nozzle diameter of 0.4 mm, print head speed of 20 mm/s, printing temperature of 225 °C, and a build plate temperature of 60 °C. Specimens were tested in the printed direction (0°, notation used in paper L) and perpendicular to the printing direction (90°, notation used in paper T). A schematic drawing of printing direction and notations used in paper is presented in Figure 2.

3 EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION

Tensile tests were performed on an Instron ElectroPuls® E10000 machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell, mechanical clamps and extensometers with gauge lengths of 25 mm (for smaller ones - printed) and 50 mm (for larger ones – cut-out), see Figure 1, used according to specimen length (Dynamic extensometer Instron 2620-601). Quasi-static tensile tests for all rectangular specimens were performed in displacement mode, with the machine's cross-head speed 1 mm/min (~0.75%/min). Before the tensile test until failure, elastic modulus was measured, by loading and unloading to 0.35% strain (see Figure 3). Tensile elastic modulus was calculated from stress-strain curves by linear fit of experimental data points in strain region 0.05-0.25%. Elastic modulus was calculated from the unloading step 2 part of the curve to reduce effects of loading, damage and developing nonlinear properties.

Tensile tests for single filament and thick filament specimens were performed on ElectroPuls® E10000 machine equipped with a 3 kN load cell, mechanical clamps in displacement-controlled mode with the cross-head speed 0.5 mm/min, (~ 0.75%/min). Since the extensometer cannot be attached to the filament specimens, strain was obtained from machines crosshead movement and machines compliance was calculated and taken into account (as described in the ASTM standard [14]).

Tensile tests were also conducted at a significantly lower displacement rate of 0.01 mm/min to evaluate the influence of loading rate on the material response.

Figure 3: Loading procedure for tensile tests

A specially designed creep recovery test was performed on an Instron ElectroPuls® E10000 machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell, mechanical clamps and a dynamic extensometer Instron 2620- 601 with a gauge length 25 mm for shorter (printed) specimens and 50 mm for longer (cut-out) specimens. Initial tests were performed without an environmental chamber. One specimen per series was tested for the short-term creep test. The short-term creep test was performed in multiple steps in a load control mode with creep periods of 10, 20, 30, and 60 min (total 120 min), followed by 10 times longer recovery period (i.e., 100, 200, 300, and 600 min, respectively). Due to the limitations of the machine, the load during recovery was kept at 3 N, which corresponds to less than 2% of the creep stress level. Loading and unloading for the creep test were done with a loading rate of 100 N/s. Depending on the stress level or the magnitude of applied load, the duration of the uploading and unloading phases could extend to 10-13 s for the strongest specimens. A schematic drawing of the loading ramp and resulting strain response can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Schematic of the creep test methodology, the representation of the creep loading steps for one stress level

Six stress levels were tested using this methodology. In order to reduce scatter due to experimental data, we used a single-specimen methodology, described in [15]. It is worth mentioning that during the entire testing procedure, the specimen was not removed from the machine, in order to avoid introducing errors due to alignment and tests are performed in increasing order of the applied stress to minimize the influence of damage on results. The strain at the end of each recovery period was assumed purely viscoplastic (VP).

4 MATERIAL MODELS

Within this study, the main focus has been on VP modeling. We have used the Zapas and Crissman model [6] where VP strain growth during loading with specified time dependence of the applied stress is given by

$$\varepsilon_{VP}(\sigma, t) = C_{VP} \left\{ \int_0^{t/t^*} \left(\frac{\sigma(\tau)}{\sigma^*} \right)^M d\tau \right\}^m \quad (2)$$

Where C_{VP} , M and m are constants to be determined experimentally, t/t^* is a normalized time where t^* is an arbitrarily chosen characteristic time constant [15]. We have used a single-specimen methodology described in [15]. Due to the previous loading history, the parameter identification is more complex than using a different specimen for each stress level. At the k -th stress level $n_k \sigma_0$, ($n_1 = 1$) assuming that all previous creep tests at lower stress levels have the same total duration time Δt_0 , VP strain is obtained as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{VP}(n_k, t) = C_{VP} \cdot \sigma_0^{mM} \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta t_0}{t^*} + n_2^M \frac{\Delta t_0}{t^*} + n_3^M \frac{\Delta t_0}{t^*} + \dots + n_k^M \cdot \frac{t - (k-1)\Delta t_0}{t^*} \right)^m \quad (3)$$

Since t^* is an arbitrarily chosen constant and the duration of all creep tests at lower stress levels is the same and t^* is taken equal to Δt_0 , thus eq. (3) can be written:

$$\varepsilon_{VP}(n_k, t) = C_{VP} \cdot \sigma_0^{mM} \cdot \left(1 + n_2^M + n_3^M + \dots + n_k^M \cdot \frac{t - (k-1)\Delta t_0}{t^*} \right)^m \quad (4)$$

In the “single specimen methodology,” data obtained from one specimen at different stress levels are analysed. Eq. (5) applied for a sequence of stress levels renders the following relationships in \ln - \ln axes:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln(\varepsilon_{VP}(n_1, t)) &= \ln(C_{VP} \sigma_0^{mM}) + m \ln\left(\frac{t}{t^*}\right), & \sigma &= \sigma_0, & t &\in [0, \Delta t_0] \\ \ln(\varepsilon_{VP}(n_2, t)) &= \ln(C_{VP} \sigma_0^{mM}) + m \ln\left(1 + n_2^M \cdot \frac{t - \Delta t_0}{t^*}\right), & \sigma &= n_2 \sigma_0, & t &\in [\Delta t_0, 2\Delta t_0] \\ \ln(\varepsilon_{VP}(n_k, t)) &= \ln(C_{VP} \sigma_0^{mM}) + m \ln\left(1 + n_2^M + n_3^M + \dots + n_k^M \cdot \frac{t - (k-1)\Delta t_0}{t^*}\right), & \sigma &= n_k \sigma_0, & t &\in [(k-1)\Delta t_0; k\Delta t_0] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

According to (5), the experimental relationship between VP strain and time has to be linear for each stress level, provided M is selected correctly. Hence, the first step in the procedure is to estimate M by varying it until the experimental data points in the \ln - \ln axes show a linear relationship. Obviously, the result of the M value is a compromise between the different “best” values for different stress levels. Afterwards, the first approximation of parameters m and C_{VP} can be found. These parameters have to be further adjusted, realizing that m has to be the same for all stress levels. Since for low stresses VP strains are small and the measurement accuracy is limited, weight factors have to be introduced, giving higher significance to accurate data fitting at higher stresses.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Tensile tests

The experimental results of the macroscale rectangular specimen tensile test are presented in Figure 5 and Table 1.

Figure 5: Tensile test results of rectangular specimens

Spec.	Rate [mm/min]	E_{mean} [MPa]	σ_{fail} [MPa]	ϵ_{fail} [%]
L_{printed}	1	3165 ± 12	48.2	1.966
L_{printed}	0.01	2987 ± 24	36.5	1.591
T_{printed}	1	2751 ± 11	31.3	1.454
T_{printed}	0.01	2570 ± 24	18.3	0.746
$L_{\text{cut-out}}$	1	2959 ± 10	46.1	1.853
$L_{\text{cut-out}}$	0.01	2921 ± 19	35.1	1.538
$T_{\text{cut-out}}$	1	2420 ± 5	13.2	0.581
$T_{\text{cut-out}}$	0.01	2437 ± 16	10.4	0.447

Table 1: Tensile test results of rectangular specimens

The results showed significant anisotropic behavior of 3D printed material. This was expected since the inner structure showed anisotropic filling of material (see Figure 1 and Figure 5).

Compared to cut-out specimens printed specimens exhibit higher values in elastic modulus, as well as greater failure stresses and strains.

The properties in longitudinal direction do not differ significantly, however, in the transverse direction, specimens cut out of the printed plate show drastic differences in properties. This shows that specimens in the transverse direction are more sensitive to the printing direction.

When comparing test speeds of 1 mm/min and 0.01 mm/min, it is observed that almost all specimens tested at slower rate (0.01 mm/min) exhibit lower elastic modulus, failure stress, and failure strain, indicating a pronounced rate-dependent viscoelastic behavior [16].

We believe that changes in properties is due to the edges, where the material tends to join together, thus presenting a more longitudinal specimen.

Figure 6: Typical side face of printed specimen [16]

The edge features of the printed specimen result from continuous pathing of the extrusion-based printing process. To initiate new lines, the print head redirects at the boundaries, forming rounded transitions. These curved edge paths, visible in the cylindrical structure (see red parts in Figure 2 and Figure 6), reflect directional changes necessary for consistent layer deposition.

Figure 7 and Table 2 show tensile test results of the thick filament as received from the manufacturer before printing, and 3D printed single filament specimens.

Figure 7: Tensile tests of thick filaments (left, Y) and single filaments (right, F)

A comparison between single filaments and thick filaments is presented in Table 2, as shown below. The single filament shows higher elastic modulus than thick filament, indicating that the properties were altered due to the printing process, which significantly influenced the mechanical behavior of the printed specimens. Similar trends can be seen also with printed specimens in L direction, where modulus is larger than the thick filaments values.

Spec.	E_{mean} [MPa]	σ_{fail} [MPa]	$\varepsilon_{\text{fail}}$ [%]
Y-thick	2546±36	41.7	4.41
F-single	3547±296	38.8	1.79

Table 2: Tensile test results of single and thick filament specimens

5.2 Creep test results

The used stress levels for creep were 10, 15, 20, 24, 28, and 32 MPa and the obtained VP strains are presented in Table 3 for cut-out specimen.

Stress, MPa	Time, min	Time t/120	VP strain, %					
			10	15	20	24	28	32
ε_0	0	0	0.000	0.005	0.007	0.021	0.044	0.093
ε_{p11}	10	0.083	0.000	0.003	0.006	0.026	0.054	0.113
ε_{p12}	30	0.25	0.001	0.003	0.011	0.034	0.062	0.135
ε_{p13}	60	0.5	0.004	0.005	0.015	0.039	0.074	0.169
ε_{p14}	120	1	0.005	0.007	0.021	0.044	0.093	0.258

Table 3: Summary of all VP strain

Figure 8: Strain development over time during creep tests at different stress levels

Curve fitting parameters has been calculated or chosen according to the Zapas and Crissman model, which has been explained in Section 4 . The obtained values are $M = 7.0$ and $m = 0.54$. The fitting of the parameter M can be seen in Figure 9. The obtained coefficients fit the experimental data at higher stress levels. At lower stress levels the experimental data are more scattered and the fit is poor. This trend is consistent with our previous tests, where values at lower stress levels do not fit the overall trend. This can be explained by the low strain values, that are close to the measuring device precision and different environmental effects on strains are higher than pure VP effects. In addition, in the initial stages of loading, the material is still aligning and thus can alter its behaviors after the initial loading steps.

Figure 9: VP strain development

Figure 10: Creep recovery strain for all stress levels (left) and for 24 MPa (right)

Figure 11: Creep compliance for all stress levels

After obtaining the values, the VP part of the curves was removed from the total strain. The obtained VE strain is presented in Figure 10. The right side of Figure 10 also shows the VE strain at all time steps for 24 MPa stress. It can be seen that the curves overlap. This can be expected, since the VE is reversible and after recovery should follow the same path as before. This indicates that the VP strain has been removed properly.

Figure 11 shows creep compliances at different stress levels. From these curves we can see nonlinear viscoelastic behavior even at low stress levels. This nonlinearity can be further increased by change in environmental effects. We noticed that a slight change in the room environment due to the changing seasons (change in temperature, humidity) significantly altered the behavior of the strain. Thus, in future studies a more controlled environment will be used to study long-term behavior of this material. The effect of temperature and humidity conditions, as well as nonlinear characterization of micro and macro scales of polymer used in 3D printing will be analyzed. In addition, the development of a robust material model for finite element analysis (FEA) is a key objective, aimed at enabling the simulation of more complex geometries. The initial phase will involve validating the material model using simple specimen geometries. Once validated, the model will be applied to more intricate shapes to investigate how various manufacturing parameters affect the nonlinear mechanical properties of 3D-printed polymers. This approach will support the advancement of predictive modeling tools for additive manufacturing applications.

Moreover, the future goal of this study will be implementing the constitutive model into FEM program like ANSYS, to simulate more complex geometries and see if the simulations have good agreement with tested specimens. Although for one-dimensional cases this has already been done on PLA specimens using ABAQUS UMAT subroutine [17].

6 CONCLUSIONS

The initial tests have shown that their printed plates have distinctly anisotropic properties. The printed specimens showed smaller deviation between directions, while specimens that were cut out of a larger 3D printed plate showed significant differences in material properties. This can be expected, since the edges of the printed specimen are more infilled, adding reinforcement in the loading direction. This is in contrary to the specimens, which were cut out of the larger 3D printed plate, where polymer is held together only by the small joint region between individual polymer filaments.

When different scales of the polymer were analyzed, it was observed that the single filament, as well as printed plates, showed slightly higher elastic modulus than the filament as received. This might indicate that the molecules have been slightly aligned within the polymer in the printing direction, creating a slight anisotropy within the material.

Initial creep tests showed that material viscoplasticity can be characterized by the Zapas model. This can also be seen from pure viscoelastic curves, where after removing the viscoplasticity, all curves coincide, showing that the reversible viscoelasticity has been recovered. The creep compliance showed nonlinear viscoelastic behavior already at relatively low stress levels of 10 MPa. Thus, nonlinear viscoelastic models have to be used to characterize these materials.

It was also noticed that the material is very sensitive to environmental conditions – a small change in outside temperature significantly affected the behavior of the polymer. Moving forward, materials have to be tested in very controlled environments, removing any changes in the strains due to the environmental changes.

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